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Structural and Biocidal Studies of Ternary Complexes of some Transition Metals

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THE paper reports the isolation, characterisation and fungicidal activity of the mixed ligand complexes (MLL') of Cu^{2+} , Ni^{2+} and Co^{2+} with *N*-pyridylanthranilic acid, Npa(L), 2-picolinic acid, PIC, and 2-furoic acid, FA(L').

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade. The metal acetate solution (0.01M in 30 ml water)

was treated with a mixture of Npa² and PIC or FA (each 0.01M in 70 ml methanol). The mixture was brought to pH 5.0–6.6 by adding 1% alcoholic ammonia solution and refluxed for 2.5 h. The resulting solid complexes were filtered washed with

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found/Calcd		μ_{eff}
	N	M	
Cu(Npa)(PIC).H ₂ O	9.87 (10.08)	15.12 (15.24)	1.92
Ni(Npa)(PIC).H ₂ O	10.15 (10.20)	14.15 (14.25)	3.26
Co(Npa)(PIC).H ₂ O	10.05 (10.19)	14.22 (14.29)	4.98
Cu(Npa)(FA).H ₂ O	6.85 (6.90)	15.45 (15.66)	2.11
Ni(Npa)(FA).H ₂ O	6.82 (6.99)	14.48 (14.64)	3.31
Co(Npa)(FA).H ₂ O	6.89 (6.98)	14.53 (14.68)	5.07

methanol and ether, dried under reduced pressure over P_2O_{10} . The elemental analysis of the metal complexes (Table 1) indicate 1 : 1 : 1 (MLL') type stoichiometry.

The molar conductance (in DMF), magnetic moments (at room temperature), ir and electronic (in DMF) spectra of the complexes were explored for their characterisation. The ligands and their metal complexes were screened² for their antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *A. flavus* and *Penicillium citrinum* in agar culture media (Table 2) at 37° for 96 h.

Results and Discussion

Low molar conductance values ($1.3-3.5 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$) suggest non-electrolytic nature of all the complexes. The solid complexes do not possess sharp melting point but decompose on heating at 200–250°.

TABLE 2—ANTIFUNGAL ACTIVITY OF LIGAND COMPLEXES

Compd.	% Inhibition at concentration (ppm) level								
	<i>A. niger</i>			<i>A. flavus</i>			<i>P. citrinum</i>		
	100	200	500	100	200	500	100	200	500
PIC	45.4	55.5	98.8	43.7	57.6	87.2	40.7	46.9	91.2
FA	38.6	45.3	85.7	33.4	49.5	78.2	32.4	40.3	85.6
Npa	56.8	68.0	70.3	65.5	72.8	75.7	60.2	69.3	74.4
Cu(Npa)(PIC).H ₂ O	65.8	79.6	—	75.3	83.7	93.4	72.4	81.8	98.3
Ni(Npa)(PIC).H ₂ O	71.3	85.4	—	79.4	89.2	—	78.3	88.4	—
Co(Npa)(PIC).H ₂ O	75.9	90.4	—	86.5	95.3	—	83.5	92.1	—
Cu(Npa)(FA).H ₂ O	68.4	82.5	92.3	80.2	86.1	96.8	70.3	80.5	96.1
Ni(Npa)(FA).H ₂ O	72.4	85.6	98.9	83.7	89.5	—	74.8	84.1	—
Co(Npa)(FA).H ₂ O	77.3	88.0	—	88.5	93.6	—	79.1	88.2	—

Carboxylic group stretching frequency of the free ligands (Npa, PIC and FA) at 1700 cm^{-1} was lowered to 1650 cm^{-1} in the complexes showing coordination of metal through carboxylate group³. The free ligand (Npa) shows a band around $3030-3300\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (NH) which is shifted to the lower frequency region in the case of complex, suggesting the coordination of NH group. The strong to medium intensity bands at $1010-1040\text{ cm}^{-1}$ are attributed to C-O-C stretch of furan ring in the free ligand. Considerable shift in case of M(Npa)(FA).H₂O complexes suggests furan ring oxygen coordination⁴. The free ligands (Npa and PIC) ring breathing modes⁵ at $\sim 1170\text{ cm}^{-1}$ shifted to lower frequency in case of the metal complexes, which indicates the coordination of pyridine nitrogen. Some new ir bands at $480-500$ and $410-430\text{ cm}^{-1}$ for the metal complexes are due to ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-N} vibrations^{6,7} respectively.

The electronic spectra of the Cu^{II} complexes exhibit a broad band at 14040 and 14188 cm^{-1} in case of Cu(Npa)(PIC).H₂O and Cu(Npa)(FA).H₂O respectively, due to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2T_{2g}$ transition in a distorted octahedral geometry⁸. This is well supported by the μ_{eff} values. The electronic spectra of Ni(Npa)(PIC).H₂O and Ni(Npa)(FA).H₂O complexes exhibit two bands, ν_1 at $9610, 9995\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and ν_2 at $16390, 16393\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The third band (ν_3) appears as a shoulder at 24690 cm^{-1} . Spectral data together with μ_{eff} value ($3.2-3.3$ B.M.) reveal an octahedral geometry for Ni^{II}⁹. The values of Racah parameter B ($816, 740\text{ cm}^{-1}$) are less than the free-ion value (1070 cm^{-1}) suggesting a considerable orbital overlap and delocalisation of electron in the metal ligand bond. ν_2/ν_1 value of 1.70 and 1.69 are close to those ($1.64-1.8$)¹⁰ expected for octahedral geometry. The electronic spectra of Co(Npa)(PIC).H₂O and Co(Npa)(FA).H₂O correspond to typical octahedral symmetry. Three bands at ($7610, 7560$), ($16339, 16337$) and ($20040, 19500$) cm^{-1} are assigned to ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F)$ (ν_1), ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F)$ (ν_2) and ${}^4T_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(F)$ (ν_3) transitions respectively. The ligand field parameters Dq , B , β and LFSE and μ_{eff} values ($4.8-5.1$ B.M.) and ν_2/ν_1 value of 1.4 and 2.16 respectively suggest distorted octahedral environment around Co^{II}.

Fungicidal screening: The study reveals (Table 2) that the ligands are fungitoxic and their activity increases with the increase in concentration. The metal complexes are more active than the corresponding free ligands. The growth inhibition capacity of the complexes follow the order, $\text{Co}^{II} > \text{Ni}^{II} > \text{Cu}^{II}$.

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Complexes of Iron(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) and Mercury(II) with 2-Hydroxy-5 methylacetophenone Thiosemicarbazone

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2-HYDROXY-5-methylacetophenone thiosemicarbazone has been used as an analytical reagent for metal ions¹. Although the preparation of some of its metal complexes and their base adducts have been mentioned^{2,3} in literature, detailed studies have not been carried out. Moreover, as we have observed some remarkable differences in composition and structure of the complexes in our investigations, we considered it worthwhile to report them along with the new complexes of Zn^{II}, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}.

Experimental

The ligand 2-hydroxy-5-methylacetophenone thiosemicarbazone (LH₂) was synthesised⁴ and recrystallised from methanol. For the preparation of the complexes of the type M(L).nH₂O, where, M=Cu^{II} or Ni^{II}, n=0.5; and M=Zn^{II}, n=0, a hot aqueous solution of the respective metal acetate (10 mmol) was added dropwise to a refluxing methanolic solution of the ligand (10 mmol) containing sodium acetate (1.0 g). The resulting solid complexes were washed with water and methanol, and dried under reduced pressure over P₂O₅. The mixed halo complexes of the metals were prepared by adding a methanolic solution of the corresponding metal halide (10 mmol) to a refluxing methanolic solution (20 mmol) of the ligand. In the cases of Fe^{III}-chloride, Cd^{II}-chloride and -bromide and